

TECHNOLOGY OF HYALURONIC ACID

N.Xoshimova

X.T.Zairova

^{1,2} Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute
Uzbekistan, Tashkent, Mirobod avenue, Oybek 45

E-mail: Khoshimova07@gmail.com

Phone: +(998)90-968-43-86

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12742536>

Introduction. Poultry is one of the most important tasks of the present day in the processing of meat and the development of unconventional technologies based on the pharmaceutical industry, especially the rational use of raw materials and the biochemical production of hyaluronic acid (HA), which is used in medicine as a wound healing and prolonging agent. Hyaluronic acid is an important fashion for the human body. It provides normal processes in the skin, eyes and joints. The unique properties of this valuable polymer were discovered a few years ago. Hyaluronic acid β -(1.3) - D-glucose acid and β -(1.4) -N-acetyl D- Glucamine is a linear non-sulfuric acid consisting of a 1:1 ratio and occurs in high organisms. Hyaluronic acid connective tissue is an important component for cell outer matrix and capillary walls. Hyaluronic acid is a much more hydrophilous compound that binds water in the form of a viscoelastic two solution.

The purpose of the study. Study of analysis of the acquisition of hyaluronic acid from the crown of the poultry

Methods and methods. Method 1. In the extraction method of obtaining gialudone acid, including the rooster pittings are grinding, extraction, combining extracts, the aqueous phase is separated, the pre-product precipitation is that before grinding, the raw material is first poured into the bloodstream in a ratio of 1:2 with ethyl alcohol, then the dissolved raw materials are additionally ultrasonically processed with a vibration frequency of 16-20 kHz for 5-10 minutes, and the extraction is 45-50 o with water for 20-25 minutes C is carried out at a temperature. The separation of the aqueous phase is carried out by vacuum filtration, the precision - 95% ethyl spirit is soaked in a ratio of 1:3, then filtered and dried the preparation. Method 2. The resulting new crown is pre-washed with freshwater in a ratio of 1: 2, and its blood is poured with ethyl alcohol. In a homogenizer, water is added to the sprinkled 100g crown at a rate of 1:3 and placed in a container of an ultra-sound vibration generator and processed for 5 minutes at a vibration frequency of 16 kHz. The mixture is then exposed to aqueous extraction at 45°C for 20 minutes. The extract is separated from the comas by vacuum filtration.

Results. From the aqueous environment, Hyaluronic acid is separated by soaking it with 95% ethyl alcohol at a rate of 1:3. The filtered brush is evaporated in a vacuum. Hyaluronic acid is stored dried at -18 ° C.

Conclusion: The recommended method of producing Hyaluronic acid significantly expands the scope of technology due to non-toxic production. It allows you to bring it as close as possible to the source of raw materials and process raw materials in every way. Decreased extraction time. Complete exfoliation of toxic solvents ensures environmental cleanliness of the technology and allows rational use of the extraction of hyaluronic acid from solid tissue residues directly for forage purposes.